

LEARNERS' ATTITUDES TOWARDS ENGLISH AS A MEDIUM OF INSTRUCTION (EMI): THE CONTEXT OF SHS IN RURAL AREAS

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Learners' Attitudes towards English as a Medium of Instruction (EMI): The Context of SHS in Rural Areas

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Abstract

This paper explored the case of senior high school students in a rural area in relation to their perception on English as a medium of instruction (EMI). This study considered the attitudes of senior high school students and implicitly described its possible relationship to the development of language proficiency among the respondents of the study. By using a survey questionnaire and structured interviews, the study aimed to describe the attitudes of senior high school students towards English as a medium of instruction. The participants showed a moderate extent of positive attitude towards EMI because they feel uncomfortable when teachers use English during lessons; The participants also showed both positive and negative attitudes toward EMI and its possible effects in their language learning. Although significant findings were derived, there is a need to further investigate the status of English as a medium of instruction in the rural contexts.

Keywords: *English as a medium of instruction, language learning, rural English speakers, language attitudes, senior high school students*

Introduction

English as a Medium of Instruction has been a significant topic of discussion at global, national, and local levels. The use of English in classrooms is seen to equip students with a language that is widely used in the global arena. This practice is not only prevalent in English-speaking countries but also in nations where English is not the first language. In some cases, like India and Pakistan, English coexists with local languages as a second language, while indigenous languages continue to be used in everyday settings (Kachru, 1992; Jenkins, 2009; Seargeant, 2012). The global importance of English has led to its widespread adoption in educational systems around the world, including the Philippines.

In the Philippines, English is commonly used as a medium of instruction. However, observations suggest that attitudes towards this practice among senior high school students vary widely. Bernardo (2004), indicated that the Bilingual Education Policy was altered to refer to the Filipino language as the language of “literacy” and “scholarly” discourse; while the English language, is referred to as the “international language” and “non-exclusive language” for science and technology.

In some contexts, a minority of students embrace the use of English in the classroom, viewing it as an opportunity to improve their language skills and prepare for future opportunities; others, however, may find it challenging, leading to a potential disconnect between English the medium of instruction and the students' comprehension as well as language proficiency. Some students may feel confident and comfortable using English, while others may struggle with it. Manh (2012) points out that when students had to learn using English in the classroom, they sometimes found it difficult to understand the subject matter and express their opinions. Moreover, factors that might influence their attitudes may include their proficiency in the language, their exposure to English outside of school, their cultural background, their attitudes towards a language and the teaching methods used by their teachers. Understanding these various factors can help educators tailor their approach to teaching English to better meet the diverse needs of their students. Similar to the Philippine setting, Indonesian learners believe that learning English is important as English is becoming one of the languages that are considered as demand languages these days (Harmer, 2007). Studies also cite pervasive influence of English as a medium of instruction across diverse academic landscapes (Smith, 2020; Johnson et al., 2018). Thus, English is also becoming increasingly popular as the language of instruction in foreign language education, especially in higher education (Dearden, 2015).

According to Chalak and Kassaian (2010), attitudes in language learning can be positive or negative. Positive attitudes are indicated by enthusiasm in language learning, while negative attitudes are shown by a lack of interest. These attitudes can significantly influence student behavior and performance, reflecting their efforts to achieve language proficiency. Additionally, a study by Bukhari, Xiao Guang, and Alikhan (2015) suggests that while students are willing to communicate in English with their friends or participate in group discussions, they may lack the confidence to communicate in unfamiliar situations.

Attitudes of students play a crucial role as they can significantly influence a student's behavior and performance. This is because students who are enthusiastic and have a positive attitude are likely to invest more effort to achieve language proficiency and those who lack interest may not strive as hard, which is indicative of a negative attitude resulting to a low language proficiency. Krashen's (1986) affective filter furthers that an individual's emotions which may include their attitudes, motivation, self-confidence and anxiety, can directly assist or interfere with the learning of a new language. Alhmali (2007) also posits that attitude is a crucial key to successful language learning, with different definitions of attitude referring to different meanings from various contexts and perspectives. This

was also highlighted by Feng and Chen (2009), who state that the learning process is an emotional process, which influences students' views and attitudes towards the learning process.

Stafford and Arias (2005) emphasized that teachers have a significant influence on students' language learning process which may indicate that the students' attitudes towards language learning is greatly shaped by their teacher. Bukhari, Xiao Guang, and Alikhan (2015) provides insight into the practical application of language learning. While students are often comfortable communicating in English within their friend circle or participating in group discussions, they may lack the confidence to communicate in unfamiliar situations. This highlights the importance of not just learning the language and using it as the medium of instruction, but also building the confidence to use it in diverse contexts.

In the study of Borlongan (2009), young generation Filipinos from a private institution were investigated in terms of their language use, attitude and identity in relation to Philippine English. It was found out that the participants particularly those who live in urban and belongs to elite class of the society prefer English as their medium of interactions in various domains, showing a positive attitude towards it. However, little is also known among learners in the rural area where the local languages are the primary medium of interactions. There could be a difference in terms of the attitudes of the rural speakers of English and the urban speakers of English.

Thus, this study aims to explore and provide meaning insights on the use of English among rural speakers of English, particularly, among senior high school students. Senior high school is a critical period among learners as they may transitioned to college students which require higher language proficiency. By understanding students' attitudes towards English as a medium of instruction during this phase could provide valuable insights for educators and policymakers, especially in the basic education curriculum. The purpose of the study about the attitude of senior high school students toward English as a medium of instruction is to gain insights about their perception, experience, and preferences regarding the use of English in the classroom.

Research Questions

This study was conceptualized with the aim of contributing knowledge in language education and language learning, particularly, in terms of the attitudes of senior high school students towards English as a medium of instruction in rural areas. Primarily it aimed to answer the following research questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, grade level, and strand?
2. What is the attitude of senior high school toward English as a Medium of Instructions (EMI)?
3. As a perceived by senior high school students, what are the effects of English as a Medium of Instructions (EMI) to their language learning?

Methodology

The study employed a descriptive research design in investigating the attitudes of senior high school students as well as its perceived effect of EMI towards the respondents' language proficiency in the light of Baker's (1992) language attitude theory. The study was conducted at San Guillermo Vocational and Industrial High School (SGVIHS) located at San Guillermo, Isabela, one of the fourth-class municipalities of the province of Isabela. The locale of the study was in a rural area where a different case in terms of language attitudes could be developing.

The respondents were senior high school students enrolled at SGVIHS. The sample size was determined using a set of criteria which includes: the students' willingness to participate, their year level, and their exposure to English as a medium of instruction. By referring to central limit theorem, there are a total of 34 individuals in the study (30 for questionnaire; 4 for interviews). Furthermore, the study utilized a researcher made research instrument which was piloted ($\alpha=0.84$) and validated by experts.

The research instrument consists 3 parts which are: the demographic profile of the respondents, questionnaire on the attitudes of senior high school students toward English as medium of instruction, and lastly the interview guide questions.

In the data gathering procedure, a letter of request asking for the permission to conduct the study was sought to the school administration. A letter of request for participation was also sought from the respondents; after which, the research questionnaires were given. Instructions were provided before the respondents answered. The questionnaires were collected and stored prior to data tabulation, analysis and interpretation. After gathering the data through questionnaire, interviews were also conducted to triangulate the results. The interview questions were asked by the researchers. The interview was also recorded using a smartphone for transcription.

Lastly, in answering the research questions, appropriate statistics were used. To answer research question 1, the researchers utilized frequency and percentage in determining the respondents' profile. In answering question number 2, mean was utilized in relation to the corresponding qualitative description of each mean range (e.g. 0.50 – 1.00 = Highly Negative, 1.51-2.50 = Negative, 2.51-3.50 = Positive, 3.51-4.00 = Highly Positive); and in answering questions number 3, simple thematic analysis was used to categorize the findings on their perceptions.

Results and Discussion

The data collected in this study was presented, analyzed, and interpreted in this section. The various findings were presented in the following tables, along with discussions and explanations.

Profile of the Respondents

Table 1. *Demographic Profile of the Respondents*

Profile Variable	f	Percentage
Age		
16 years old	9	26.47%
17 years old	14	41.17%
18 years old	7	20.58%
Others	4	11.76%
Total	34	100 %
Gender		
Female	16	47.05%
Male	14	41.17%
Others	4	11.76%
Total	34	100%
Grade Level		
Grade 11	20	58.82%
Grade 12	10	29.41%
Others	4	11.76%
Total	34	100%
Track		
Academic-HUMSS	10	29.41%
TVL	20	58.82%
Others	4	11.76%
Total	34	100%

The table 1 presents the profile of the respondents providing insight into their age, sex, grade level, and track. In terms of age, the data shows that a majority of the respondents are aged 17 (41.17%), followed by 16 years old (26.47%), 18 years old (20.58%) and lastly, those who participated in the interview were classified as others (11.76%). The distribution suggest that the surveyed population consists of primarily high school students in their late adolescence. When it comes to gender, the data reveals that there is slightly higher percentage of female respondents (47.05%) compared to male respondents (41.17%). This gender distribution highlights the importance of considering gender specific perspective and experience when analyzing the survey results, especially in terms of attitudes, however, in this study, no test of correlation or difference will be employed.

In terms of grade level, a majority of the respondents are in Grade 11 (58.82%), while the remaining (41.17%) are in Grade 12 and those who participated in the interviews. This distribution indicates that the sample population is predominantly composed of students in their second-to-last year of high school.

In terms of track, the data shows that a majority of the respondents (58.82%) are enrolled in the TVL (Technical-Vocational-Livelihood) track, while 29.41% are in the Academic-HUMSS (Humanities and Social Sciences strand).

Overall, the data provides information about the surveyed population, including their age distribution, gender, grade level, and track. These demographic characteristics are important considerations when analyzing the survey results and understanding the perspectives and experiences of the respondent.

Attitudes of senior high school students in a rural area towards English as a medium of instruction (EMI)

Table 2 presents the findings on the attitudes of senior high school students in a rural area toward English as a medium of instruction (EMI). It can be seen in the table that a majority of the respondents showed a positive attitude towards English as a medium of instruction (EMI) ($m=2.97$). The statement "English is important for my future career prospects" yields a mean score of 3.27, indicating a positive attitude among the respondents. Also, the statement "Using English as a Medium of Instruction prepares me better for the future", suggest that EMI is beneficial among the respondents. These findings suggest that the respondents recognize the significance of English as the medium of instruction (EMI) for their future career opportunities; the respondents understand that having strong English language skills can positively impact their career prospects and that they feel positive about English as a medium of instruction. EMI could also be considered in providing both knowledge of the subject content as well as English language skills (Tang, 2020). Also, students might also think that this will make them more globally competitive individuals in the global job market (Galloway, 2017).

However, despite showing positive attitude toward EMI, the mean scores seem to reveal a low extent of positive attitude towards English as the medium of instruction indicated by the total mean ($m=2.97$). In fact, two statements yield negative results; these statements are "I feel comfortable using English as a Medium of Instructions by my teacher" and "I enjoy using English to communicate with friends and peers inside the school where English is used as the medium of instruction". This means that the respondents expressed a negative sentiment towards the idea of feeling comfortable using English as the medium of instruction by their teachers. In other

words, the respondents generally do not feel comfortable with their teacher using English as the primary language for instruction. It is not a highly negative sentiment, but it is clear that there is some discomfort or unease associated with this practice. These findings are consistent with the challenges highlighted by Manh (2012), who points out that students may struggle to understand the subject matter and express their opinions when the teachers have to teach using English and students have to learn using English in the classroom.

Table 2. *Attitudes of Senior High School students towards EMI*

<i>Statements</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. I feel comfortable using English as a medium of instruction by my teacher.	2.43	Negative
2. Using English as a medium of instruction prepares me better for the future.	3.23	Positive
3. English as a medium of instruction enhance my understanding of the subject matter.	2.93	Positive
4. English language as a medium of instruction positively impacts my academic performance.	3.17	Positive
5. My teachers use English as a medium of instructions, it improves my English skills.	3.2	Positive
6. I feel confident when I speak English in class since it is the medium of instruction.	2.9	Positive
7. Teachers who use English as a medium of instruction are good English speakers.	3.13	Positive
8. I have been given enough support to improve my English skills in classes, where English is used as a medium of instruction.	2.97	Positive
9. I enjoy using English to communicate with friends and peers inside the school where English is used as the medium of instruction.	2.47	Negative
10. English is important for my future career prospects.	3.27	Positive
11. I feel motivated to improve my English skills for social interaction	3.03	Positive
12. Using English in academic settings help me feel more confident in my abilities	2.93	Positive
13. English language skills are essential for accessing global information and resources	3.03	Positive
14. I feel comfortable expressing myself in English during social interaction.	2.97	Positive
15. I enjoy participating in English language activities and even outside of the classroom.	2.83	Positive
Total	2.97	Positive

Legend: 0.50 – 1.00 = Highly Negative; 1.51 – 2.50 = Negative; 2.51 – 3.50 = Positive; 3.51 – 4.0 = Highly Positive

In terms of peer interaction in relation to the use of English inside the classroom, the respondents also expressed a negative sentiment towards using English when they interact with their friends or peers. This probably stems from their preferred language, which could be influenced by their locale – rural and urban. In urban cases, learners comfortably use English in their casual conversations, particularly those belonging to elite families. In this study, learners might opt to use their local language present in the locale in various domains such as when they communicate with their friends or peer outside and inside the classroom instead of English as their medium of interaction. These findings might suggest that the respondents feel anxious about using English when they talk to their peers or when their teacher taught their lessons. Haskin (2003, as cited in Male, 2018) defines language anxiety as a feeling of uneasiness, self-doubt, lack of confidence, aggravation, or fear that could also be complexly intertwined with self-esteem. Cooke et al. (2006) posits that when learners feel anxious or have anxiety, they tend to change their behavior from willingness to study to unwillingness to study or might find difficulty in concentrating; thus, this might implicitly affect their attitudes towards English as the medium of instruction.

Moreover, the findings of this study also reflect the learners' belief on language learning, teacher-learner interactions as well as personal and interpersonal relations which might indicate language anxiety which coincides with Ying (2008), Kabigting and Nanud (2020), and Zhang and Zhong (2012). Thus, their language attitudes might be a reflection of language anxiety in this particular sense or vice versa.

Perceived Effects of English as a medium of instruction (EMI) to Language Learning

Table 3. *Perceived effects of EMI among the respondents towards Language Learning*

<i>Themes</i>
Wider access to learning/ content comprehension
Language exposure
Develops language proficiency

Table 3 presents the findings on the interviews on the perceived effects of English as a medium of instruction among the participants towards language learning. It can be seen in the table that there are three themes in terms of the perceived effects of EMI in language learning which are: wider access, language exposure, and develops language proficiency.

It can be subsumed that the participants believed that English as a medium of instruction facilitates more advanced and proficient learning as it would provide the learners a wider access to a wide range of resources, contributing to overall knowledge and everyday learning experience; it can be seen in the given extract.

Participant 1: *Using English as medium of instruction helps students have a more advanced and proficient learning and it opens a door to wider access of resources.*

Participant 4: *...it can enhance proficiency in English; it can also improve access to global knowledge and resources.*

Similar to the findings of this study, Pun and Jin (2002) states that when English is used as a medium of instruction, learners tend to benefit more in terms of content comprehension.

Language exposure is also crucial to language learning; having quality language input could improve the language abilities of the learners as well as their language proficiency. The participants believe that being expose to English helps them develop proficiency as can be seen in the extract.

Participant 2: *It can provide[s] learning with exposure in English language...also it can develop their speaking skills. They can also easily understand their lesson and expand their knowledge in grammatical pattern in English.*

Moreover, in the study of Hoff et al. (2012), they investigated the possible influence of language input and exposure to the development of bilingual learners; and it was found out that as the learners received language input through exposure to the target language, learners also develop their vocabulary and grammar relative to the amount of input. This finding coincides with the findings of this study in which language exposure is seen as one of the factors that could affect the participants language learning experience through English as a medium of instruction.

Overall, the effects of using English as a medium of instruction in language learning, as perceived by the respondents, include wider access to learning, content comprehension, language exposure and develops language proficiency; thus, a balanced approach to language instruction can address these challenges by providing effective language support, differentiated instruction, integration of language skills, cultural inclusivity, and a supportive learning environment.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study has investigated the attitude of senior high school students in a rural area towards English as a medium of instruction (EMI). The findings provide valuable insights on their attitudes towards English as a medium of instruction, and their perceptions of the effects of English as a medium of instruction on their language learning.

In terms of the attitudes of senior high school students towards English as a medium of instruction, the findings indicate a low extent of positive attitude towards EMI.

In the interviews, the findings highlight three themes which are: wider access, language exposure, and develops language proficiency, as the respondents also expressed positive perceive effects towards English as medium of instruction in terms of its effect to their language learning.

Based on these findings, the following recommendations are proposed:

Enhance English language activities by providing a variety of engaging and interactive English language activities that cater to the interests and needs of the students. These activities should be designed to promote active participation and enjoyment, both within and outside the classroom.

Provide language support which offers additional language support and resources to improve students' English language proficiency; this could include language workshops, tutoring sessions, online resources, and language exchange programs.

Foster a supportive classroom environment which creates a positive and inclusive classroom environment where students feel comfortable expressing themselves in English that encourage open communication, provide constructive feedback, and promote a non-judgmental atmosphere. This will help alleviate any discomfort or unease associated with using English as the medium of instruction.

Conduct a wider range study regarding language attitudes towards EMI that could represent a particular sample and generate a generalizable finding.

By implementing these recommendations, educators, stakeholders, students and future researchers can work together to improve the attitudes of senior high school students towards English as a medium of instruction. This will lead to enhanced language skills, increased enjoyment in English language activities, and improved overall confidence and comfort level in using English as the medium of instruction. Ultimately, these efforts will contribute to the students' success in their academic pursuits and future works.

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